

Interview Protocol

INTRODUCTION

Thank you for participating in this interview. As you already know from my email, I am researching the maturity of process mining as an analytic capability. Your opinion will contribute to understanding this concept and the associated challenges. This study aims to create a maturity model in process mining as analytic capabilities.

RECORDING INSTRUCTIONS

I would like to record our interview to simplify the note-taking process and ensure that no information is lost. Your answers and comments will be processed and reflected in any research outcome (e.g., papers) anonymously. The information you provide will only be used for this research. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may stop at any time.

GENERAL INSTRUCTIONS

This interview will be done in several steps as follows:

1. I will ask general questions about your background and understanding of the topic. This will be buried if you already filled in the Google form that I sent you beforehand.
2. In the second part, I will show you two case studies of the company that uses process mining and how we can measure their performance using a preliminary maturity model that we have already prepared (around 10 minutes). I already sent the case study and the detail of our preliminary model measurement to your email.
3. We will discuss the maturity model that I already show, how it is relevant to the daily problem faced in an organization and whether there is any dimension that is not yet covered in the case studies (around 30 minutes)
4. In the third part, I hope I will try to elicit some feedback on how I can develop this maturity model to be more suitable for more organizations in various stages of process mining implementation.

I expect to cover all questions within 60 minutes. If there is anything unclear during the interview or you wish to clarify something, do not hesitate to interrupt me.

A. Questions after Case Study Explanation

After you see the illustration of the maturity model, we will discuss the maturity model.

1. What do you think about the dimensions of the maturity model? Are they too many or too few? Do you think the dimensions are understandable?
2. Is there any other dimension you think needs to be added?

3. What do you think about the subdimensions and the level of the maturity model? Are they too many or too few? Do you think the dimensions are understandable?
4. Is there any other sub-dimension you think needs to be added?
5. Do you think seeing the application of the model can be beneficial for the company's management?

B. Questions about maturity model development

This part will discuss the feedback and suitability of the preliminary maturity model to different organizations/company conditions.

1. Do you think your organization/ company can implement this kind of maturity model?
2. Is there any possibility of resistance to performance measurement in the company? Why?
3. In terms of technology, which step is your organization now?
 - (i) PM Initiated
 - (ii) Diagnostic and Descriptive,
 - (iii) Predictive
 - (iv) or Prescriptive?
4. Based on your experience, what do you think is most important before implementing Process Mining?
5. What kind of tool do you need to guide the company to improve the level? (Guidelines, assistance with consultants, in-house training, manual book, self-assessment checklist etc.?)